

ENGLISH READING STRATEGIES FOR LAW STUDENTS

Ravshanova Oyshabonu

Teacher of law school of Navoi region

Phone: +998(94) 251 66 55. ravshanova.oyssha1@gmail.com

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Abstract. *Students and professionals feel that learning English is necessary to stay competitive in their studies and careers due to the rapid globalization of the world. We are also living in the age of specializations. Individuals possess specialized knowledge in various domains; the most effective approach to acquire this kind of information is by learning several languages, particularly English, which is widely utilized globally. The study examined the impact of using English for Specific Purposes reading within the framework of the communicative approach, and the results were presented in this article for a group of law students. Results demonstrate that specialized reading encourages students to use English in everyday contexts and expands their vocabulary and knowledge of their particular field of study.*

Key words: *law students, ESP, specialized reading, communicative approach.*

СТРАТЕГИИ ЧТЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ-ЮРИСТОВ

Аннотация. *Студенты и специалисты считают, что изучение английского языка необходимо, чтобы оставаться конкурентоспособными в учебе и карьере в связи с быстрой глобализацией мира. Мы также живем в эпоху специализаций. Люди обладают специальными знаниями в различных областях; Самый эффективный способ получения такого рода информации — изучение нескольких языков, особенно английского, который широко используется во всем мире. В исследовании изучалось влияние использования чтения на английском языке для специальных целей в рамках коммуникативного подхода, и результаты были представлены в этой статье для группы студентов-юристов. Результаты показывают, что специализированное чтение побуждает учащихся использовать английский язык в повседневном контексте и расширяет их словарный запас и знания в конкретной области обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *студенты-юристы, ESP, специализированное чтение, коммуникативный подход.*

ESP might be described as a specific branch of English as a foreign language on the training of students in specific areas, Anthony (2007) points out that English can be used in academic studies or the teaching of English for travel or professional purposes, which represents a population of professionals who are involved in their own fields of study; hence, they need to delve deep into specific topics, and the ESP approach can be useful as a learning methodology.

Setting up ESP, students were encouraged to find more information that piqued their interest by practicing reading within the confines of the communicative approach. They also had the chance to practice other skills, like listening to their partners, conversing about shared interests, debating and discussing the readings according to their own ideas, and summarizing and composing their own opinions. These assignments gave me a better understanding of the students' work and enabled me to make study-specific conclusions. The process of learning English has

been changing according to the students' needs. ESP has been an important component of that change; according to Anthony's (2007) experience, teachers are much more aware of the importance of needs analysis in order to select materials that are closely related to the learner's goals. Thus, we can infer that advanced and adult learners feel the need to acquire knowledge of their own fields of study. Hence, English became a tool to acquire information from different disciplines such as engineering, architecture, computer science, health, environmental protection, mechanics, accounting, and economics, among other fields.

The communicative approach is predicated on the notion that effective language learning results from communicating "real" meaning; consequently, when learners engage in authentic communication, their innate language acquisition strategies are activated, which expedites their language learning process.

Based on this, Hutchinson and Waters (1987, p. 25) state that ESP is "an approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to content and method are based on the learner's reason for learning," meaning that students are aware of their own learning process and the significance of learning a second language when the teacher incorporates their disciplines into class activities. Similarly, Jin, Singh, and Li (2005) discovered through their own research that one of the responsibilities of the teacher in the classroom is to develop strategies to aid students in understanding texts. This method is a productive way to comprehend the readings and the primary concepts. This finding gets me to thinking about how crucial it is for teachers to encourage and support their students' work as well as to support reading practice in ESP.

Considering that the communicative approach is the material because it is the teachers' primary resource is another crucial component of reading ESP. "Authentic materials are important tools for use in ESP classes because, as we have clearly shown, they motivate and immerse learners in specific areas of the target language in which practice is needed," write Torregrosa and Sánchez-Reyes (2011, p. 93). Because they are rich in content and typically based on actual experiences and investigations, real texts are therefore always preferred. In order to give students authentic reading materials, Jin et al. (2005, p. 19) recommend that teachers assist students in gaining access to authentic English language materials, which may be found online, in international newspapers, or in magazines. These resources give students knowledge about various countries, people groups, cultures, and linguistic topics. As a result, through the use of authentic materials, students are able to demonstrate their language proficiency, improve their background knowledge, and engage in genuine communication.

Apart from adhering to the guidelines of the communicative approach, this study considers the reading process (pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading), whereby students accomplish an effective task:

- Pre-reading prepares students to read efficiently, which facilitates comprehension and is related to students' backgrounds. Lebauer (1998, p. 5) notes: "Pre-reading activities can improve students' cognitive burden while reading because prior discussions will have been incorporated."

Thus, teachers have to provide supplemental activities such as brainstorming, differencing, guessing, and analyzing titles and pictures, among other activities.

- While-reading allows students to carry out "active reading" with activities such as arguing, summarizing, questioning, evaluating, and comparing the text with their own personal

experience. It is necessary that students avoid using dictionaries while engaged in these activities; however, teachers can encourage students to use strategies such as skimming and scanning for faster and more in-depth reading practice. At the same time, Ur (1996) and Vaezi (2001) suggest such strategies as making predictions, integrating prior knowledge, re-reading, making use of context or guessing, breaking words into their component parts, reading in chunks and monitoring one's reading.

- Post-reading exercises depend on the purpose of reading and the type of information the reader is interested in gaining. With reference to the previous statement, Barnett (1988, p. 5) remarks: "Post-reading exercises first check students' comprehension and then lead students to a deeper analysis of the text." Finally, reading has to accomplish the function of imparting new knowledge in tandem with activities such as group discussion, summarizing, questioning, filling out charts, completing a text, listening to or reading other related materials, and role-playing.

Hence, students must have the autonomy to choose the best techniques for them, according to their own needs and learning styles.

Because they lack the vocabulary necessary to read, write, or speak the language, students are often afraid to practice it. However, this research helped the students overcome this fear by teaching them how to apply various reading comprehension techniques. Barnett (1988) suggests using prereading, while-reading, and post-reading processes that involve activities like finding cognates, guessing, skimming, scanning, mapping, and outlining, among other things. As a result, the students used these strategies to help them comprehend the texts as well as to develop a specific vocabulary that would come in handy when it came time to write summaries or give oral reports.

By reading about subjects linked to their chosen careers, students were able to develop a broad perspective on the world outside of their field of study. This allowed them to select pertinent information based on their interests, such as Uzbekistan's constitution, human rights, drug use and abuse, divorce, crime and punishment, and other subjects.

Furthermore, this study encourages students to look into information about their personal needs in other countries, which will be helpful in their future careers.

As their careers progress, law students must acquire particular skills, like the capacity to present, debate, evaluate, and defend their positions in light of their personal experiences or expertise. The methodology used in this study provided students with the appropriate conditions for carrying out these processes through different reading activities. Furthermore, this research motivated the students' use of prior knowledge as a relevant source to defend their ideas in front of their peers, who were their close competitors and judges.

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